

THE INFLUENCE OF THE ORIGINAL STATE OF FIBERS ON THE MICRO-MORPHOLOGY OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The perfection of liquid-infiltration as well as microstructure and morphology intensively influence on the properties of fiber reinforced metal matrix composite (FRM). The bad wettability between fiber and matrix alloy always lead to form uneven distribution of fibers, incomplete infiltration and other defects in composite with liquid-infiltration. Studies to solve the problems were usually dealing with parameters of liquid-infiltration process, surface treatment of fiber and matrix alloying. In fact, the original state of fibers play an important role in the perfection and equality of FRM with liquid-infiltration.

In this paper, three original states of fibers, i.e. spontaneous arranged, network fixed with coating hybridized with particles in the preform were studied. It has been found experimentally that incomplete infiltration is existed when fibers are arranged spontaneously, although infiltrating defects can be reduced by raising the liquid-infiltrating pressure, but it can't be eliminated completely. In the case of fibre network fixed with coating, the filling of fine corners in preform were achieved in advance and then the preform can be infiltrated rather completely at low pressure. Finally, by the hybrid with the particles, the fiber bunch is separated and the dead corners are almost eliminated. So the infiltration process of preform is perfect. Comparing with fiber network fixed with coating, in the hybrid preform the fibers appear more separating and it causes well-distributed in the composite.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced metal matrix composite (FRM) has advantages of high specific strength and specific modulus, good size stability and high-temperature properties, which has great potentiality of widely application in aviation, aerospace, electronics and other industry. These performances depend on the micro-morphology and structure of metal matrix composite. The bad wettability between fiber and matrix alloy always lead to incomplete infiltration, uneven

distribution and other defects formed in composite with liquid-infiltration. Studies to solve the problems were usually dealing with parameters of liquid-infiltration, surface treatment of fiber and matrix alloying^{[1] [2]}. In fact, the original state of fibers play an important role in the perfection and equality of FRM with liquid infiltration.

For this reason, it was studied in this paper the influences of original states of monofilaments in the fiber-bunch preform on the perfection of liquid-infiltration and the micromorphology of composites, to probe the formation mechanism and controlling method of the defects and fiber distribution of composite, and try to find out a new way to gain good properties of fiber reinforced metal matrix composites.

1. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

1.1 THE ORIGINAL STATE CONTROL OF FIBRES

Carbon fiber with 6~8 μ m diameter and each bunch consisted of 3000 fiber monofilaments was selected as reinforcement. Matrix was casting aluminium alloy A356 (Al-7wt pct Si-0.3 wt pct Mg). The original states of fiber monofilaments in the bunch were:

(1) Spontaneous arrangement :

Fiber bunches were arranged in the direction of liquid infiltration in the mould after remove the size on the fiber monofilaments surface were arranged spontaneously in the bunch.

(2) Network fixed with coating:

Fiber monofilaments have a network structure in the bunch were connected with SiC coating. from which the monofilaments were separated each other and the fine corners in the bunch were eliminated^[3].

(3) Hybrid with particles:

The hybrid preform with fiber and particle was obtained by putting SiC particles (with 3 μ m diameter) in the fiber bunches rely on ultrasonic soaking method to separate the fiber monofilaments in the bunch.

1.2 PREPARATION AND ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE SAMPLES

The composite samples were prepared by liquid infiltration technique under the pressure of 1.0MPa and 8.6MPa. The pre-heating temperature of preform was 600 °C and the temperature of liquid alloy was 750 °C. EPM-810Q electron probe microscope and SEM-515 scanning electron microscope were used to analysis the infiltrating effect and the micro-morphology of the composite.

2. EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1 SPONTANEOUS ARRANGEMENT

With the spontaneous arrangement of monofilaments in fiber bunch, the morphology of composite was formed as fig1. after liquid infiltration.

With low infiltrating pressure there are a lot holes in the fiber bunch and little of metal; with high infiltrating pressure the fiber bunch had been filled nearly completely, but small crevices still remained in the contact area between two fibers, e.g. there are unfilled place in the composite.

(a) liquid infiltrating pressure 1.0MPa

(b) liquid-infiltrating pressure 8.6MPa

Fig.1 Infiltrating effect in the fiber bunch with spontaneous arrangement of fibers

There are many kinds of resistance in the processing of liquid alloy infiltrates fiber preform, and the infiltrating effect depends on the level of resistance and the ability of exert infiltrating pressure to overcome these resistances. The infiltrating resistances are equal with the same technique parameters except infiltrating pressure.

The higher of the pressure, the more perfect the infiltrating effect in this circumstance, so the difference between fig.1(a) and (b) is inevitable. It is worth noticing that such a high pressure (8.6MPa) of infiltration still could not make liquid alloy infiltrates completely the space in fiber bunch, and the preheating temperature of fiber T_f and the temperature of liquid alloy T_m were very high (even higher than the melting point of alloy). It was obvious that the filling perfection would be influenced by the arrangement of monofilaments in the bunch. Since the preform consists the size difference between the cavities in the bunch and among the bunches, that cause the different filling speed of liquid alloy infiltration. The filling speed of liquid alloy was faster in the bigger space among the bunches and slower in the bunch.

After the liquid alloy had filled the cavity among the bunches, it flowed traverse into the bunch (vertical to the fiber), it means that the filling process in the bunch consisted of traverse and longitudinal direction. In fact, the traverse flowing of liquid alloy pushed the monofilaments be more close in spontaneous arrangement.

Considering the contact point of two equal fibers, a cross-section in which is given in Figure 2 with the definition of geometrical variable. The pressure required to fill transversely in this contact area is [4] :

$$P = \frac{\sigma_{LA}}{R} \sin(\theta - \alpha - \pi/2) \sin(\alpha) \operatorname{tg}(\alpha/2) \quad (1)$$

where σ_{LA} is the liquid alloy/atmosphere interfacial energy, θ is the contact angle. Under this experimental conditions (preheating temperature of preform was 600 °C, temperature of liquid alloy was 750 °C) aluminium alloy could not wet the fiber, e.g. $\theta > 90^\circ$ [5]. At the contact area α approaches zero, e.g. $\sin(\alpha) \rightarrow 0$, and $\sin(\theta - \alpha - \pi/2) > 0$, so the filling pressure becomes infinitely large, e.g. complete infiltration is impossible in thermodynamics. Therefore, when liquid alloy can't wet the fiber, it is evident at any high infiltrating pressure the incomplete infiltration of the preform with spontaneous arrangement of monofilaments in fiber bunches, and the infiltrating defects are inexorable in the composites.

Fig.2 Infiltration of the contact area between two fibers by a non-wetting alloy

2.2 NETWORK FIXED BY COATING

It is shown from expression (1) that the nearer from the contact point, the higher the infiltrating pressure required, and required pressure is finite in the area far from the contact point. If the formation of fibers surface coating is controlled so suitably that the area near the contact point is filled with coating, means the cavity is almost eliminated in where α approaches zero, it would reduce the highest infiltrating pressure of liquid alloy required to completely fill the remain cavity. In this circumstance fibers were linked by coating just like network, so it is called network fixed by coating. Figure 3(b) is the metallographical morphology of the composite in which the fiber monofilaments were network fixed with SiC coating under lower infiltrating pressure. It shows that the cavity near the contact point had been filled by alloy and coating together, and there is no hole in the composite comparing with Fig1.

In addition, network structure protects the traverse squeeze to the fibers by the flowing of liquid alloy, since the filling passage in fiber bunch can not become narrow, and it would be beneficial to the liquid infiltration.

(a) Design for network coating

(b) Infiltrating effect of fibres network fixed with coating

Fig.3 Design and infiltrating effect of network coating

But the gathering of fibers and the netting of coating do harmful to the properties of composite under this circumstance, especially when the coating is brittle. And the bonding force is very small in the contact area, causes even more detrimental to the traverse property of composite.

2.3 HYBRID WITH PARTICLES

Figure 4 shows the metallograph of composite formed with liquid alloy infiltrating hybrid preform. Comparing with spontaneous arrangement of monofilaments figure 1(b) and network by coating figure 2(b), the fiber monofilaments in the bunch are separated and has no contact point. Every monofilament was encircled by metal and there was no hole defect in the composite, means perfect infiltration has been achieved in the fiber bunch.

Fig. 4 Infiltration effect of hybrid preform

In fact, for fibers arrange spontaneously, monofilaments contact each other form a thin sharp corner-gap, i.e. the blind corner; and the sharp corner gaps are filled up by coated layer in the network; but in the hybrid arrangement particulates are used to isolate the fibers, so fibers are uncontacted each other, and make blind corners to be eliminated. In the other hand, existence of particulates in fiber bunch produce an effect to resist the squeeze force caused by the traverse infiltrating pressure against fibers. So that the channel for the filling is maintained, and the

contacting between particles and fibers can be considered as a point contact. Owing to the fact, there was a certain fixed distance among the particulates along the direction of fibers, and the distance don't resist the traverse filling of liquid alloy, contrary for the network coating does resist the traverse filling of liquid alloy between bunches and in a bunch because of the continuity of coating layers.

Perfect infiltrating can be realized in the case network coating, but it had a unfavorable effective to the properties of composites. By the using of the hybrid on the particulates and fibers perfect achieves not only infiltrating, but also makes fibers isolated each other and disperses homogenously. It is obviously that hybrid preform network has an excellent effect on properties of composites.

3. CONCLUSION

(1) While bunches of fibers with spontaneously arrangement filled by poor wettable metal liquid, it is inevitable that infiltrating defects are existed in composites. There are many holes in the bunch with low pressure infiltrating, even the filling is more completely at high pressure, but the places where fibers contact each other are still holes. Theoretical calculations and experimental results prove that this kind of holes can't be eliminated by the increase of pressure.

(2) While network structure is used to make hollows of fibers-contacting-point filled, so the preform of fibers can be infiltrated completely in a low pressure, but the gathering of fibers and the netting of coating layers is unfavourable for properties of composites.

(3) The fiber monofilaments can be isolated each other, and filling blind corners are able to be eliminated, where hybrid preform is used. Compared with network structure, the hybrid preform is beneficial to be filled with liquid, especially the traverse filling, and makes fibers in composite isolated each other and dispersed. Eventually, the properties of composite made by hybrid are higher than that of other techniques.

REFERENCES

1. Nourbarhsh S. et. al, *Metallurgical Transaction A*, **20A**, 2257-2263(1989)
2. Wang Haowei et. al, *Acta Aeronautica et Astronautica Sinica*, **14(8) B**, 435-438(1993)
3. Wang Haowei et. al, *J. Northwestern Polytechnical University*, **10(3)**, 279-284(1992)
4. Mortensen A., *Metallurgical Transactions A*, **18A**, 1160-1163(1987)
5. Laurent V. J., *Material Science*, **22**, 244-250(1987)